

A Study on the Problems of Pre-Marital relationship in India

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Abstract :

Choosing their partners, deciding with whom they will share their lives, family building, family responsibility, and living with their partners are some of the duties of young adulthood period. Pre-marital relationship period is a period for two different people who do not know each other, to know and understand each other and create bonds of love which are necessary to live together before they take the decision to marry. Women and men should try to understand the real identity, expectations, and characteristics of both themselves and the candidate partner's in the pre-marital relationship period.

Introduction :

Human beings go on their lives as a member of small or large groups. The most important one of these groups is family which is called a special small group and provides a continuation of human species. Compliance with certain conditions, we can create families with at least two individuals of the opposite sex to choose each other as partners. Choosing their partners, deciding with whom they will share their lives, family building, family responsibility, and living with their partners are some of the duties of young adulthood period. Pre-marital relationship period is a period for two different people who do not know each other, to know and understand

each other and create bonds of love which are necessary to live together before they take the decision to marry. Personal, social, and legal facilities such as friendship before marriage and engagement are for the purpose of fulfilling this fact. Taking a decision to marry is a complicated process. People's desire to make their physical, emotional, and social needs real is among the important factors that lead people to marriage. Women and men should try to understand the real identity, expectations, and characteristics of both themselves and the candidate partner's in the pre-marital relationship period.

Need of the Study :

This study explores the problems in Pre-marital affairs and we all well know about the marital relations between a male and female. As per Psychology Male attracts female and females attracts male. In Modern India we see through news papers or local dailies regarding the news contents on Problems of Pre-marital affairs. This type of relations may harm the family, Body, Social behavior, etc. So, a step has taken through this study to explore the different types of Problems in Pre-marital relations.

Problems in Pre-marital affairs :

1. The pre-marital relationship may lead to infidelity :

Having shared close physical intimacy with a person may increase the likelihood of infidelity after the relationship has run its course. Say we and our partner part ways, and we move on with another person. However, somewhere down the line, this old flame comes back into our life. This is when the negative effects of pre-marital sex creep in.

2. One tends to lose interest in the partner :

Pre-marital sex means becoming physically intimate with a partner you're not married to. This intimacy gives us both a chance to explore our sexual desires in every way possible. There is a good chance that what our experience in these sexual encounters with our partner may be very different from our expectations and vice-versa.

3. High possibility of a breakup :

If one tends to lose interest in the partner or feels sexually dissatisfied in the relationship, the chances of a breakup naturally go up. A lack of sexual compatibility may make the entire relationship lose value, and the disgruntled partner may decide to call it quits for good.

4. Pre-marital sex affects other relationships in a negative way :

One of the reasons not to have sex before marriage which is worth considering is that you'll have to put our self through a lot of trouble to sustain a good sex life. If you're sexually active before marriage, chances are that you're getting our action on the sly. Like most Indian families, there's a lot of hush-hush around the idea of girlfriends or love before marriage.

5. Pre-marital relationships can disrupt our mental health :

Pre-marital relationships do weigh on our mind and can be a trigger for stress. The negative effects of pre-marital sex do include effects on our own mental health. The guilt of keeping secrets from our family and friends, the nagging fear of unwanted pregnancies, risk of STIs can all contribute to stress buildup.

6. High risk of STDs :

The hormones are raging; there are sparks flying and intense emotions at play. All of these factors can trigger an insatiable lust and in that moment, all we see is the advantages of pre-marital sex and all that we said above probably won't even come to mind.

7. One tends to take the partner for granted :

A lot of times physical intimacy is seen as a defect of long-term commitment to the relationship. Once you've been intimate with our partner, it is possible that they become too secure about the future and stop putting as much effort into the relationship as before. Living with the realization of being taken for granted can become a root cause for discord, leading to constant bickering and fights.

8. Pre-marital sex can change our outlook toward love :

This happens when we get physical intimacy is followed by heartbreak. We were physically and emotionally invested in the relationship. Perhaps, we were young and this was one of those fairytale romances where we automatically imagine a happily ever after. Then, our partner falls out of love and move on, and the cruel reality of life hits home.

9. Self-esteem takes a hit :

It might become so guilt-ridden about the pre-marital relationship, especially if things don't work out between the partners, that it may send one self-esteem plummeting. The risks associated with and the dangers of pre-marital relationships will eventually percolate into our everyday existence.

Conclusion :

Pre-marital relationships are often viewed as spaces of acute individualism or as a social phenomenon that can be a threat to the values and norms of the family. However, through this paper, I have argued that pre-marital experiences in fact mirror marital expectations, duties, and templates as the family comes to scrutinize and shape these relationships. Furthermore, this paper also highlights that the intimacies of the middle class youth and their ideals in India like country for marriage are evolving in contexts that are gendered and also influenced by processes of modernization such as the use of technology, global styles of life.

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